

Decomposition of Hydrogen Peroxide Catalysed by Cobalt Sulphate in Presence of Beryllium Oxide

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Catalytic decomposition of hydrogen peroxide has been studied using cobalt sulphate in presence of beryllium oxide. Considerable enhancement in the decomposition is found which otherwise with simple cobalt sulphate as catalyst is small. The results have been interpreted utilising a formation of a surface product and its subsequent interaction.

DECOMPOSITION of hydrogen peroxide has been studied using mostly the oxide, the hydroxide, some insoluble salts and various complexes of cobalt as the catalyst¹⁻³. Use of hydrated cobalt ions has generally been neglected probably because of their poor catalytic influence⁴. It has been found recently that a considerable improvement⁵ takes place if these ions are employed as surface adsorbed species. Attempt is now made to examine the catalytic influence of these ions in presence of beryllium oxide. The possible variation in the rate of decomposition, due to changes in the concentration of cobalt ions on one hand and the amount of beryllium oxide on the other, has also been studied.

Experimental

Method and material: Beryllium carbonate (E. Merck) was dissolved in hydrochloric acid and treated with ammonia solution to precipitate the corresponding hydroxide; this, after washing repeatedly with hot distilled water and drying, was heated at 800° for 4 hrs. The resulting oxide was sieved for particles of 100-120 (BSS) mesh size. Prior to use in any experiment, the sample was activated at 300° for 4 hrs and then allowed a rest period of 24 hrs.

Stock solution (0.05 M) of cobalt sulphate was prepared using AnalaR grade (BDH) sample and was standardised following recommended procedure⁶. Experimental solutions of the desired concentration were obtained by usual dilution.

Hydrogen peroxide solutions of the required concentration were obtained similarly from dilution of its concentrated (BDH 30%) sample.

A weighed quantity (0.5 g) of beryllium oxide was kept in contact with 5.0 ml of (0.025 M) cobalt sulphate solution at 30°. To this was then added 5.0 ml of (~8 vol) hydrogen peroxide, and the volume of oxygen evolved was measured at various time-intervals, using a gasometric technique⁶. Experiments were repeated at other temperatures (25°-40°) also. The results for the rate constant, k

[calculated from the plots of log (a-x) versus time] are given in Table 1. Here a represents the volume of oxygen evolved on completion of the decomposition and x that at any time, t.

TABLE 1—DECOMPOSITION OF HYDROGEN PEROXIDE CATALYSED BY COBALT SULPHATE IN PRESENCE OF BERYLLIUM OXIDE

Amount of hydrogen peroxide—5.0 ml (~8 vol)
Catalyst—0.5 g beryllium oxide and 5.0 ml of 0.025 M cobalt sulphate

Temperature °C	Rate constant k (min ⁻¹) × 10 ³	Energy of activation (k cal mole ⁻¹)
25	4.17	
30	6.67	26.0
35	8.76	
40	18.16	

Using a constant amount of hydrogen peroxide the influence of variation in the composition of the catalyst, on the rate of decomposition, was studied next. This includes changes in (i) the amount of beryllium oxide and (ii) the concentration of cobalt sulphate solution. In the first series of experiments, the catalyst consisted of 5.0 ml of 0.025 M cobalt sulphate and various amounts of beryllium oxide (0.2 to 0.8 g); in the second, concentration of cobalt sulphate was varied (0.01 to 0.05 M) while the amount of beryllium oxide was kept constant (0.5 g). The values for the rate constant are given in Table 2. For the study of the variation in the concentration of H₂O₂ (4.5-9 vol) the catalyst consisted of 5.0 ml of (0.025 M) cobalt sulphate solution and 0.2 g of beryllium oxide. The results are shown graphically in Fig. 1 as plots of log (a-x) versus time.

Results and Discussion

The decomposition of hydrogen peroxide, in the use of the present catalyst, proceeds in a first order manner which is evident from Fig. 1. The set of curves indicates that the values of k (varying between 1.92 - 1.78 × 10⁻³ min⁻¹) may be taken to be independent of H₂O concentration over the range

TABLE 2—CATALYTIC DECOMPOSITION OF HYDROGEN PEROXIDE: INFLUENCE ON RATE, OF THE VARIATION IN THE AMOUNT OF COBALT SULPHATE AND BERYLLIUM OXIDE

Temperature— $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$
 Volume of hydrogen peroxide—5.0 ml
 Volume of cobalt sulphate solution—5.0 ml

A		B	
Amount of beryllium oxide—0.5 g	Concentration of cobalt sulphate solution— $2.5 \times 10^{-2} M$	Amount of beryllium oxide (g)	Concentration of cobalt sulphate solution— $2.5 \times 10^{-2} M$
Concentration of cobalt sulphate solution ($M \times 10^3$)	$k(\text{min}^{-1}) \times 10^3$	Amount of beryllium oxide (g)	$k(\text{min}^{-1}) \times 10^3$
1.00	3.56	0.2	2.05
1.25	3.92	0.4	4.23
1.67	4.99	0.6	6.14
2.50	5.42	0.8	6.71
5.00	6.14		

Fig. 1. Decomposition of hydrogen peroxide catalysed by cobalt sulphate (5.0 ml of 0.025M) and 0.2 g of beryllium oxide. Concentration of H_2O_2 (A : 9, B : 6.3 and C : 4.5 vol).

studied. Energy of activation, calculated from the corresponding Arrhenius plot, is found to be 26.0 kcal mole⁻¹.

The results now obtained indicate that the catalytic decomposition is enhanced markedly when a small amount of beryllium oxide is present together with cobalt sulphate which otherwise without the oxide is very much inappreciable. Thus the volume of oxygen evolved from 5.0 ml (~8 vol) of hydrogen peroxide in a time period of 4 hrs is only 2.0 ml when 5.0 ml (0.025M) of cobalt sulphate is used as the catalyst; on providing 0.5 g of beryllium oxide additionally, the volume of oxygen obtained in only 30 minutes becomes 36.2 ml. It is to be noted that the same amount of beryllium oxide when used singly gives only 2.5 ml of oxygen. It is thus evident that the oxide and cobalt sulphate both exhibit poor catalytic effects individually but interact in presence of hydrogen peroxide to

produce an active species responsible for the enhanced decomposition.

The value of the rate constant k , in the use of the present catalyst, is seen to depend on actual composition of the catalyst. A plot of k either against the concentration of cobalt sulphate (as used with a constant amount of beryllium oxide) or against the amount of beryllium oxide (as used with a constant concentration of cobalt sulphate) is linear over the range of variations studied (Table 2). Extrapolation to zero value gives a small intercept indicative of the fact (*vide supra*) that both the constituents of the proposed catalyst are capable of catalysing the decomposition though very poorly. This is in agreement with the above conclusion that the species responsible for the enhanced decomposition is produced only when both of these interact in presence of hydrogen peroxide.

Further support to this conclusion is obtained from the observation of a colour change in the surface appearance of beryllium oxide the moment it comes in contact with both of these (i.e., cobalt sulphate and hydrogen peroxide) together: no such change however, is observed when beryllium oxide is in contact either with cobalt sulphate or with hydrogen peroxide singly.

That the sulphate ions do not exert any appreciable catalytic influence is confirmed in separate experiments using sodium and potassium sulphates both alone as well as together with beryllium oxide. This indicates that mainly the cobalt ions are involved in the formation of the above mentioned catalytically active surface product.

Attempts made to dissolve it out from the surface (for analytical aims) by use of acids were unsuccessful because it decomposed on such treatments. It could however, be preserved (intact on the surface as such) in evacuated vessels for some time. Ir absorption studies (made using this sample) indicate that the surface species is not a simple addition product⁷ containing hydrogen peroxide (absence of any band around 550 and 880 cm^{-1}).

Formation of such a surface product and its involvement in enhancing the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide may be understood from the considerations of Ram and Prasad⁸ proposed recently and now adopted in a form to suit the present requirements. These workers have utilised the interaction of the absorbed species with the free radicals generated from H_2O_2 .

Cobalt ions when come in contact with the oxide surface, adsorption takes place and soon an adsorption-equilibrium is established. As a result of interaction of this with H_2O_2 , the surface product is obtained as shown below:

A product of the same type [i.e., Co(III)HO_2^-] has also been reported by Bexandale and Wells⁹ to

be formed during the interaction of Co(III) with hydrogen peroxide.

The step to follow next produces the free radical OH together with OH⁻ ion; the latter neutralises with the H⁺ ion produced in (i) providing thus the availability of OH.

Subsequent reaction of the surface product with OH produces oxygen and regenerates at the same time, the starting ion-adsorbed surface to be ready for repeating the above sequence of reactions.

Thus the processes, producing the surface product and regenerating the original ion-adsorbed surface, proceed alternately as long as hydrogen peroxide remains available; on its complete consumption further formation of the surface product ceases.

From the above, it is apparent that the formation of the surface product depends on the extent of adsorption and the concentration of H₂O₂. On the basis of the observed kinetic results the rate law may be represented in the following way :

$$-\frac{d[\text{H}_2\text{O}_2]}{dt} = k[\text{surface-Co}^{3+}][\text{H}_2\text{O}_2]$$

The first term, being dependent on the availability of the oxide surface and the concentration of cobalt ions, may be taken as fixed for any experiment starting with definite quantities of the oxide and cobalt sulphate. Consequently the rate

may be expressed as follows :

$$-\frac{d[\text{H}_2\text{O}_2]}{dt} = k'[\text{H}_2\text{O}_2]$$

It may be expected from the above that a variation either in the amount of beryllium oxide or the concentration of cobalt sulphate should affect the extent of adsorption and therefore the rate of the decomposition of H₂O₂. Results obtained using different amounts of beryllium oxide and different concentrations of cobalt sulphate (Table 2) are in agreement.

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